

SYNTHESIS OF BIODEGRADABLE POLYURETHANES NANOCOMPOSITES BY FUNTIONALIZATION OF REACTIVE SILICATES

L. Rueda^a, I. Garcia^a, T. Palomares^b, A. Alonso-Varona^b, I. Mondragon^a and A. Eceiza^a

^a ‘Materials + Technologies’ Group, Dept. of Chemical and Environmental Engineering, Polytechnic School, University of the Basque Country. Pza. Europa 1, 20018, Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain

^b Dept. of Celular Biology and Histology, Faculty of Medicine and Odontology of the University of the Basque Country. B° Sarriena, s/n, 48940 Leioa-Bizkaia, Spain
lorena.rueda@ehu.es, arantxa.eceiza@ehu.es

SUMMARY

Biodegradable and biocompatible polyether-polyester urethanes with different hard segment contents and their nanocomposites were synthesized using different amounts of modified montmorillonite, Cloisite[®] 30B (C30B). Analysis of thermal and mechanical properties as well as morphological characterization was carried out by means of different experimental techniques. Biocompatibility and biodegradability studies were also performed.

Keywords: functionalization, biocompatibility, atomic force microscopy (AFM).

INTRODUCTION

In general, inorganic nanocomponents offer enormous advantages over traditional macro- or micro-particles due to their higher surface area and aspect ratio, improved adhesion between inorganic additives and polymer, and lower amount of loading to achieve equivalent properties if the nanometric size inorganic is finely dispersed within the polymeric matrix producing a nanocomposite [1, 2].

Segmented thermoplastic polyurethanes (STPU) have been incorporated in a number of biomedical devices due to their excellent mechanical properties and adequate biocompatibility [3]. STPU are linear block copolymers typically constructed alternating soft and hard segments (SS and HS), which can form microphase separately structure under appropriate conditions [4]. The polyurethane versatility has conducted towards many diverse industrial applications [5] and also by varying the structure of segmented polyurethanes, the mechanical properties can be tuned towards specific clinical applications. Moreover, polyurethanes have been useful in medical devices because they demonstrate a combination of toughness, durability, flexibility, biocompatibility and biostability [6].

In the last years, polymer nanocomposites using natural clays type montmorillonite which consist of layered silicates, have attracted a great deal of attention because of the improvements in the mechanical, thermal, and gas barrier properties of the polymer [7]. Montmorillonite is natural clay belonging to the 2:1 phyllosilicate and the crystal structure is made of two silica tetrahedrally fused to an edge shared octahedral sheet of either aluminium or magnesium hydroxide. These silicates self-organize to form stacks with a regular van der Waals gap between the intergalleries. The existence of ionic bonds (e.g. Al³⁺ replaced by Mg²⁺ or Fe²⁺ generates negative charges that are

counterbalanced by cations like Na^+ , Ca^{2+} or K^+) and the ability to form hydrogen bonds with water make montmorillonite highly hydrophilic and incompatible with organic polymers [8]. The effect of the addition of organoclays on property improvement is related to the morphology structure and dispersion efficiency of the organoclay particles in the polymer matrix, which is associated with the compatibility between the polymer and the organoclay. For this reason, to achieve optimal dispersion of the silicates in the polymer is of prime importance to modify the montmorillonite with various organic cationic molecules (which are defined as swelling agents) to render the silicates organophilic [9]. These swelling agents can be directly involved in the polymerization process and resulted in exfoliated structures of silicates in the polymer [10]. In this work, the organically modified montmorillonite used is Cloisite[®] 30B whose swelling agent to synthesized the polyurethane nanocomposites react through the hydroxyl functional groups ($-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{OH}$) with the isocyanate groups ($-\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{O}$).

On the other hand, when reviewing the literature on the polymer nanocomposites based on different inorganic particles, we found only a limited number of papers describing the in vitro biocompatibility testing of well-characterized polyurethanes [11,12]. In vitro testing procedures are a fundamental part of any material evaluation and the direct contact assays using fibroblasts are also frequently used for the determination of the cellular response toward biomaterials.

In the present contribution, the evaluation of nanoclays functionalization and their incorporation into biocompatible synthesised polyurethanes has been performed. The characterization of biocompatible matrix and their nanocomposites has been carried out by means of different experimental techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Polyurethane synthesis

New segmented thermoplastic polyurethanes with different hard segment contents were synthesized in bulk by two steps reaction procedure using poly (caprolactone-b-polytetrahydrofuran-b-caprolactone) diol (PCL-b-PTHF-b-PCL) as soft segment, 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) and 1,4 butanediol (BD) as chain extender to form the HS. The first step of polyurethane synthesis was carried out at 100 °C for 6 h in N_2 atmosphere mixing the polydiol and the HDI and subsequently, in the second step, BD was added for 5 min. The reaction was completed in a vacuum oven at 100 °C for 24 h.

Functionalization of modified montmorillonite and nanocomposites preparation

C30B modified with an organic quaternary ammonium ion $\text{N}^+(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH})_2(\text{CH}_3)\text{T}$ has been provided by Southern Clay Products (USA). Kinetic studies of functionalization of silicate nanoclay C30B via clay-monomer/prepolymer reactions were carried out by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). For this reason, several aliquots were extracted at different times and washed by centrifugation in tetrahydrofuran (THF). On the other hand, polyurethane nanocomposites containing 18 wt % HS (STPU-18) were synthesized in situ in THF. Different amounts of reactive C30B (1-4 wt %) sonicated in THF (Vibracell 75043, Bioblock Scientific) were incorporated together with the polydiol at the first step of the reaction following the same synthesis conditions used for matrix preparation.

CHARACTERIZATION

Infrared spectroscopy

Attenuated total reflection Fourier transform infrared (ATR-FTIR) spectroscopy was used to characterize the functional groups of the polyurethane and their nanocomposites using a Nicolet Nexus FT-IR with a KRS-5 for attenuated total reflection prism and an angle of 45°.

Thermogravimetric analysis

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA/SDTA 851 Mettler Toledo) at a scanning rate of 10 °C/min from room temperature to 600 °C under nitrogen atmosphere was used to analyze the reaction between C30B and –NCO groups and the resulting polyurethane matrix and their nanocomposites.

Dynamic mechanical analysis

Test samples for dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) were prepared by compression molding. The samples were uniformly spread into a mould and subjected to compressing-decompressing moulded for five times in order to remove any air bubbles at 100 °C and finally they were cooled to 25 °C. The probes for DMA analysis (24x3x1 mm³) were cut from the pressed films and were evaluated in a DMA 7e equipment (Perkin Elmer) using the three points bending geometry at a frequency of 1 Hz and a scanning rate of 5 °C/min from -100 °C to room temperature using an initial strain of ~ 0.05 %.

Atomic force microscopy

Tapping mode atomic force microscopy (AFM) was used to visualize the images of STPU nanocomposites on a Nanoscope IIIa, Multimode, Digital Instruments with an integrated force generated by cantilever/silicon probes, applying a resonance frequency of ~180 kHz. The cantilevers had a tip radius of 5-10 nm and 125 µm long. The samples were dissolved in DMF (1 wt %) and the films were prepared via spin-coating (Spincoater P6700) at 2000 rpm for 130 s. The samples were subjected to annealing in an oven at 100 °C for 12 h.

In vitro cell response

To assess the short-term cytotoxicity of the developed polyurethanes, STPU-18 and STPU-18-2, L-929 cells were seeded in 96-well microplates at a density of 4x10³ cells/well and allowed to attach and grow in standard conditions for 24h. Cultures were then treated for 24, 48 and 72 h with the materials conditioned mediums. To provide the basis for comparison of the effects of the test materials, according to ISO 10993-12, we also used a negative control (High-density Polyethylene, USP Rockville, USA), a positive control (Polyvinyl chloride, Portex Ltd, UK) and, finally, standard culture medium (Control). Viability was determined by a colorimetric assay (Cell Proliferation Kit I, Roche) which measures the metabolic activity of viable cells. The cell number per well was proportional to the absorbance recorded ($A_{550\text{ nm}} - A_{690\text{ nm}}$) using an ELISA plate reader. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) studies were carried out on cultured L929 fibroblasts on both STPU-18 and STPU-18-2 films and control surfaces. Aliquots containing 5x10⁴ cells were seeded on top of the polyurethanes, placed previously in 24

well flat bottom culture plates (Costar). After 24 h, samples were fixed with 2 wt% glutaraldehyde in cacodylate buffer (0.1 M, pH = 7.4) and post-fixed in OsO₄ for 1 h, washed in PBS and dehydrated using series of graded ethanol solutions. Samples were dried through the CO₂ critical point, gold sputtered and observed in a Hitachi SEM (Hitachi S-3400N).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of this work have been divided into two principle parts, on one hand, synthesis and characterization of the polyurethanes as matrix, and on the other hand, synthesis and characterization of nanocomposites based on polyurethane containing 18 wt% of hard segment. Table 1 summarizes the designation of all the materials together with the molar ratio of the reactives involved in the polymerization.

Table 1. Designation of the synthesised polyurethanes and their nanocomposites, molar ratio of the involved reactives, hard segment content of the polyurethanes and percentages of C30B incorporated into the matrix.

Polyurethane	Molar ratio PCL-b-PTHF-b-PCL:HDI:BD	Hard segment (wt% HS)
STPU-18	1:2:1	18
STPU-25	1:3:2	25
STPU-32	1:4:3	32
STPU-42	1:6:5	42
Polyurethane nanocomposites	Molar ratio PCL-b-PTHF-b-CL:HDI:BD-C30B	Contents of C30B (wt%)
STPU-18-1	1:2:0.990:0.01	1
STPU-18-2	1:2:0.980:0.02	2
STPU-18-4	1:2:0.960:0.04	4

Polyurethanes as matrix

Typical infrared spectra of synthesised polyurethanes are shown in Figure 1. It is possible to observe bands in two principal vibrational regions: the ν_{NH} stretching vibration (3200-3500 cm⁻¹) and the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ stretching vibration in the amide I region (1637-1730 cm⁻¹). In order to study the influence of the hard segment on the formation of hydrogen bonding, Figure 2 shows an amplification of the C=O amide-I stretching region and the analysis of the areas was carried out using deconvolution Gaussian curves of the peaks. As expected, an increase in the hard segment content involves a decrement in band I, corresponding to the fraction of free carbonyl group at 1730 cm⁻¹ (% area $\nu_{1730 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$), which can correspond to carbonyl groups from the neat poly(ester-ether)diol and also to non H-bonded carbonyl groups from the polyurethane. In addition, the fraction in relation with the band III, associated with the ordered (“crystalline”) hard domains at 1685 cm⁻¹ (% area $\nu_{1685 \text{ cm}^{-1}}$) increases with hard segment content as a result

of the formation of large HS domains that contribute in the phase separated microstructure.

Figure 1. ATR-IR spectra of thermoplastic synthesised polyurethanes

On the other hand, the stretching band at 1716 cm^{-1} , band II, linked to weaker interactions or less ordered structures, suggests that interurethane interactions are more influential in polyurethanes with low hard segment content, when the average hard domain size increases. It could be due to the H-bonded ester carbonyl groups which are covalently bonded nearly to the short hard segment, thus causing the formation of disordered hard segment domains [13]. In this case, it is necessary to take into account that some hard segments can dissolve in the soft phase thus affecting phase mixing, which is thermodynamically possible due to the similar values of solubility parameters (δ) of polydiol ($21.9\text{ J}^{1/2}/\text{cm}^{1/2}$) and HDI/1,4-BD ($23.0\text{ J}^{1/2}/\text{cm}^{1/2}$) [14].

Figure 2. ATR-IR spectra showing the carbonyl group absorbance region (band I-IV): band I (% area $\nu_{1730\text{ cm}^{-1}}$), band II (% area $\nu_{1716\text{ cm}^{-1}}$), band III (% area $\nu_{1685\text{ cm}^{-1}}$) and band IV (% area $\nu_{1650\text{ cm}^{-1}}$) of STPU-18, STPU-25, STPU-32 and STPU-42.

From this point of view, the band II associated to disordered hard domains (% area $\nu_{1716\text{cm}^{-1}}$) shows the highest value for STPU-25, which could be related with a major phase mixing on boundaries of hard/soft segments. In the case of polyurethanes with higher HS content, STPU-32 and STPU-42, the band III increases and in consequence it produces a decrement in the value of the areas related to bands I and II, indicating that the hard segments formed by more HDI/1,4-BD units decrease the interactions between hard/soft segment boundaries and provoke phase separation of the domains. For this reason, STPU-42 shows a high ordered structure due to the incorporated long hard segments chains and this fact may involve changes in properties/morphology, as shown below for thermal and morphological properties.

Figure 3 shows DMA results of STPU samples. The glass transition temperature of the soft phase (T_{gSS}) is defined as α transition in $\tan \delta$ curve in DMA tests and can be used as an indicator of the degree of phase separation [15-17].

Figure 3. Loss factor and storage modulus vs. temperature of the STPU-18 (\blacktriangle), STPU-25 (\blacksquare), STPU-32 (\blacklozenge) and STPU-42 (\bullet).

In this way, the slight increase in T_{gSS} in the different polyurethanes could be indicative of the result of the chain extension occurring during the first step of polymerization and also denotes a relative small amount of hard segment is mixed in the soft domains [18], which depend on the excess of HDI. Besides, as the hard segment content increases a broadening in the loss peak reflects that different lengths of hard segment bonded to soft segment chains can be formed, thus affecting to their molecular mobility. From this point of view, whereas STPU-25 shows an increase in T_{gSS} value due to the significant chain extension or the influence of small segments of hard segment in the soft phase, in STPU-32 and STPU-42 the T_{gSS} decreases, approaching the value of glass transition temperature for neat polydiol (T_{gSS}), resulting in a microphase separated structure of covalently bonded hard/soft domains, as observed before by ATR-IR results. On the other hand, Figure 3 also shows that the increase in hard segment content in the polyurethanes causes an increment in the storage modulus.

The degradation analysis was carried out using TGA. Urethanes were known to be relatively thermally unstable materials and the decomposition temperature of the urethane bond depends on the polyurethane structure. Normally, three mechanisms of decomposition of urethane bonds have been proposed and reactions may proceed simultaneously: dissociation to isocyanate and alcohol, formation of primary amine and olefin and formation of secondary amine and carbon dioxide [19-22]. Furthermore, at higher temperatures, the weight loss is associated with others segments of the remaining

structure. Figure 4 presents the thermal degradation behaviour of thermoplastic polyurethanes at different hard segment contents.

Figure 4. Weight losses and their corresponding derivatives vs. temperature for the different polyurethanes.

TG curve shows that weight losses of STPUs occur from 250 °C to 480 °C. The corresponding derivative curves reveal only one peak for the polyurethane with low SS content (STPU-18) whose maximum thermal degradation takes place at 400 °C and two main degradation processes for polyurethanes with higher HS content which begins to appear at 250 °C and is indicative of the hard segment degradation residues. Thermal stability of STPUs depends strongly on urethane groups per unit volume and an increase in the initial weight loss was observed as a result of the increase in the amount of urethane groups. All polyurethanes degraded totally at around 500 °C.

Nanocomposites based on STPU-18

Different functionalization methods to verify the urethane linkage formation between $\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$ functionalities of C30B and -NCO end groups from prepolymer chains or from HDI monomer was investigated by TGA. The samples were exhaustively washed with THF eight times and dried at room temperature during 2 days before TGA analysis. It is worth nothing that in all cases, the weight loss was higher when the reaction time is increased which is indicative of progressive anchorage on C30B surface.

Figure 5. TGA of different modified C30B via functionalization reactions with HDI (method I), HDI+polydiol (method II) and prepolymer (method III) after 60 minutes.

Figure 5 shows the thermograms of the aliquots extracted after 60 minutes by different functionalization methods. The higher weight loss observed by method II (HDI+polydiol+C30B) indicates that the introduction of the nanoclay at the first step of the polymerization facilitates their inclusion in the nanocomposite synthesis reaction and the exfoliation process, improving the interactions between polymer matrix and the nanoreinforcement at the interphase.

DMA was used to evaluate the viscoelastic response of the STPU-18 and nanocomposite materials synthesised by method II with different clay contents measuring the elastic modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan \delta$).

Figure 6. Loss factor and storage modulus vs. temperature of the STPU-18 (■), STPU-18-1(▲), STPU-18-2 (●) and STPU-18-4 (◆).

Figure 6 shows that for all the nanocomposites, an increase in clay content resulted in a significantly shift in $\tan \delta$ towards a higher temperature and can be attributed to better interactions between matrix and platelets of the clay, which restrict the mobility of the soft segment chains. In addition, nanocomposites based on high clay contents show an increase in the storage modulus compared with the pure STPU-18 which is due to the mechanism reinforcement by inorganic material.

Figure 7. AFM images of nanocomposites containing 1 and 4 wt % of modified C30B, STPU-18-1 and STPU-18-4 respectively.

AFM images were used to examine the clay dispersion in polyurethane matrix. Figure 7 shows AFM images of STPU-18-1 and STPU-18-4 nanocomposites. For the nanocomposites containing 1 wt% of C30B, AFM images showed effective clay dispersion and evidence clay particles clusters was not observed. Similar images were observed at 2 wt% clay content. At higher clay contents, a relatively uniform dispersion of C30B was observed in STPU-18-4 but obvious intercalated structures can be observed. This effect can be explained because of at low clay content the organically modified C30B sheets were easily exfoliated and dispersed in the matrix due to the reaction between hydroxyl groups presented in C30B and $-NCO$ groups. As clay weight fraction increase, intercalated clay appears due to the limited volume space in the matrix and higher viscosity, thus resulting in not enough and unevenly dispersion.

Figure 8. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) micrographs, carried out on cultured L929 fibroblasts on both STPU-18 and STPU-18-2 films. (Scale bar 50 μ m).

Figure 8 shows SEM images obtained from cells seeded on top of the synthesised materials STPU-18 and STPU-18-2. As can be seen, L-929 fibroblasts massively colonized the STPU-18 surface, were they proliferate and are well adhered, showing that this material is a good substrate for cell adhesion and proliferation. In the case of STPU-18-2, whereas proliferation of fibroblasts cultured in conditioned medium was not significantly altered when compared to the matrix, the degree of adhesion to material surface was dramatically reduced as can be observed in the SEM image.

CONCLUSIONS

The thermal, physical and morphological characterization of the synthesised polyurethanes allows to concluding that hard/soft domains lengths control the thermodynamical compatibility between segments and in consequence, the structure/properties relationships. Thus, the increase in HS content provokes microphase separation as can be observed by deconvolution technique applied to the carbonyl region in attenuated total reflection infrared spectroscopy (ATR-IR) measurements. On the other hand, the anchorage of $-NCO$ groups provided by monomer/prepolymer reactions in the nanoclay was evaluated by TGA, which confirmed the functionalization in C30B. In this way, polyurethane nanocomposites with different percentages of well-dispersed C30B were produced. DMA results showed an increase in the glass transition temperature, T_{gss} , corresponding to the soft segment when the C30B content increased also resulting in higher elastic modulus. In addition, according to AFM, exfoliation/intercalation was achieved in composites containing C30B. Finally, proliferation of fibroblasts cultured in STPU-18 suggested that these materials as strong

candidates for biomedical applications, whereas STPU-18-2 showed a significant altered structure and in consequence, the degree of adhesion to material surface was dramatically reduced.

Acknowledgements. The authors wish to express their gratitude to the University of Basque Country for funding this work (PIFA/01/2006/045), to the Basque Government 'Etortek 2005/BiomaGUNE 2005' (IE05-143), 'Saiotek 2007' (S-PE07UN02), 'Health Dept.' (PI-2005-111043) and also 'Grupos de Investigación Consolidados' (IT-365-07).

References

1. I. Garcia, A. Tercjak, L. Rueda, I. Mondragon. *Macromolecules* 2008; 41: 9295–9298.
2. S. Kumari, A. K. Mishra, A.V.R. Krishna, K.V.S.N. Raju. *Prog. Org. Coatings* 2007; 60: 54-62
3. J.P. Santerre, K. Woodhouse, G. Laroche, R.S. Labow. *Biomaterials* 2005; 26: 7457–7470.
4. L. Rueda-Larraz, B. Fernandez d'Arlas, A. Tercjak, A. Ribes, I. Mondragon, A. Eceiza, *European Polymer Journal* 2009 (in press).
5. A. Pattanayak, S. Jana. *Polymer* 2005; 46: 3275-3288
6. Y.I. Tien, K.H. Wei. *Macromolecules* 2001; 34: 9045-9052
7. J Xiong, Z Zheng, H Jiang, S Ye, X Wang. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 2007; 38: 132-137.
8. Y.I. Tien, K.H. Wei. *Polymer* 2001; 42: 3213-3221.
9. Y.W. Chen-Yang, Y.K. Lee, Y.T. Chen, J.C. Wu. *Polymer* 2007; 48, 2969-2979
10. A. Pattanayak, S.C. Jana, *Polymer Engineering and Science* 2005; 45: 1532-1539
11. K.E. Styan, D.J. Martin, L.A. Poole-Warren. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research Part A* 2007; 86A: 571-582.
12. B. Van Minnen, B. Stegenga, M.B.M. Van Leeuwen, T.G. Van Kooten, R.R.M. Bos. *Journal of Biomedical Materials Research* 2006, 76A, 377-385.
13. D.J. Skrovanek, P.C. Painter, M.M. Coleman. *Macromolecules* 1986, 19, 699-705.
14. Van Krevelen DW. *Properties of polymers*. Van Krevelen DW. Amsterdam: Elsevier Scientific Publishing Co., 1990, p. 189-225.
15. B. Fernandez d'Arlas, L. Rueda, K. De la Caba, I. Mondragon, A. Eceiza. *Polymer Engineering and Science* 2008; 48: 519-529.
16. C.B. Wang, S.L. Cooper. *Macromolecules* 1983; 16:775-786.
17. H. Tan, M. Guo, R. Du, X. Xie, J. Li, Y. Zhong, Q. Fu. *Polymer* 2004, 45:1647–1657
18. R.W. Seymour, S.L. Cooper. *Journal of Polymer Science C Polymer Letters* 1971; 9: 689-694
19. I. Javni, Z.S. Petrovic, A. Guo, R. Fuller. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 1999; 77: 1723-1734.
20. J.W.C. Van Bogart, D.A. Bluemke, S.L. Cooper. *Polymer* 1981; 22: 1428-1438.
21. S. SolarSKI, S.Benali, M. Rochery, E. Devaux, M. Alexandre, F. Monteverde, P. Dubois. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science* 2005; 95: 238-244.
22. M. Berta, C. Lindsay, G. Pans, G. Camino. *Polymer Degradability and Stability* 2006; 91: 1179-1191.